
Adaptive LoRA Merging for Efficient Domain Incremental Learning

Eric Nuertey Coleman*
Department of Computer Science
University of Pisa
eric.coleman@phd.unipi.it

Luigi Quarantiello*
Department of Computer Science
University of Pisa
luigi.quarantiello@phd.unipi.it

Julio Hurtado
Centre for Applications of Mathematical & Computing Sciences
University of Warwick
julio.hurtado@warwick.ac.uk

Vincenzo Lomonaco
Department of Computer Science
University of Pisa
vincenzo.lomonaco@unipi.it

Abstract

Merging Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA) has become an essential centre for research and development. However, it is unclear how these methods behave in dynamic scenarios like Domain Incremental Learning (DIL). Here, we address a key limitation of current merging algorithms: their overreliance on fixed weights that usually assume equal importance across tasks. Our method dynamically computes the coefficient for merging, allowing for continuous adaptation to new domains while adjusting the influence of previous ones. We evaluated our approach against some current state-of-the-art merging algorithms on two DIL benchmarks: PACS and OfficeHome. Our results show that the adaptive merging technique achieves performance comparable to or superior to fixed-weight methods while eliminating the need for manual weight selection. In particular, our method maintains high accuracy with minimal memory requirements, using as little as one sample per class for coefficient learning. This work showcases a promising use of LoRA adapters and merging algorithms in continual learning, providing a valuable direction for future research.

1 Introduction

Large pre-trained models have become the default solutions for several applications that require Machine Learning, mainly given the great diversity of problems in which these models can perform effectively. However, these models need to be adapted to perform well in most downstream tasks, due to the fixed and limited training distribution. In classical fine-tuning, all network weights are modified to adapt to the new task, which is highly time-consuming and computationally expensive, considering the massive size of these models. Additionally, the large number of weights that need to be adjusted could easily lead to overfitting.

*Equal contribution

One alternative to classical fine-tuning are *Parameter-Efficient Fine-Tuning (PEFT)* methods. PEFT techniques aim to adapt large models to specific tasks by updating a tiny portion of the network’s weights, generally obtaining comparable performance to the fine-tuning approach but much more efficiently [2]. As traditional learning methods, PEFT works under the strong IID assumption, meaning that the training distribution must be kept constant throughout the training process, supposing that the whole set of samples is available from the beginning. This limitation makes it difficult for current models to be used in dynamic contexts, where future distributions can change.

To tackle such constraint, *Continual Learning (CL)* [5] focuses on continuously training a model as the training distribution changes. The goal is to make machine learning models capable of absorbing new knowledge while reducing the *catastrophic forgetting* of the previous tasks. Although some papers relate CL to PEFT, they mainly focus on Prompts, leaving out other methods such as LoRA [3].

In this work, we focus on a *Domain-Incremental Learning (DIL)* scenario and how to use adapters merging techniques. While different methods have been proposed for merging models, it still needs to be determined which method is most effective in CL settings. This study examines and compares several approaches for merging these continually trained adapters. We also propose a new method to dynamically find the importance of the task when merging the models that adapt to dynamic environments. Our results show that we can achieve comparable or even better results than state-of-the-art methods but with less hyperparameter selection and more robustness in terms of performance.

2 Background

Low Rank Adaptation (LoRA): LoRA [3] is a PEFT technique that allows large pretrained models to adapt to downstream tasks by modifying only a small subset of the model’s original parameters. LoRA introduces trainable matrices $A \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times d}$ and $B \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times r}$ to model weight updates:

$$W = W_0 + BA \tag{1}$$

where W_0 is the pre-trained weight and $r \ll \min(d, k)$ is the adapter rank. By training these low-rank matrices, LoRA significantly reduces the number of trainable parameters while maintaining comparable performance to full fine-tuning.

Merging Algorithms: Several algorithms have been developed for merging specialized models:

- **DARE** (Drop And REscale) [12]: This technique addresses parameter redundancy by sparsifying and merging fine-tuned models. It focuses on delta parameters ($\delta = W_{fine-tuned} - W_{pre-trained}$), randomly dropping a high percentage (e.g., 90% or 99%) and rescaling the remaining ones by $1/(1 - p)$, where p is the drop ratio. DARE enables the merging of multiple task-specific models, potentially outperforming individual source models.
- **TIES-MERGE** [11]: This algorithm addresses interference when combining multiple fine-tuned models through a three-step process: 1) Trimming insignificant parameter changes, 2) Electing signs to resolve conflicts, and 3) Merging parameters aligned with the agreed-upon sign. This approach minimizes interference between task-specific adaptations while maintaining model coherence.
- **Task Arithmetic** [4]: This method introduces Task Vectors, defined as $\Delta W = W_{ft} - W_{pt}$, where W_{ft} and W_{pt} are fine-tuned and pre-trained weights, respectively. These vectors enable operations like negation ($-\Delta W$), addition ($\Delta W_A + \Delta W_B$), and analogy ($(\Delta W_B - \Delta W_A) + \Delta W_C \approx \Delta W_D$), allowing for flexible model behavior modification and knowledge transfer between related tasks without direct training.

Continual Learning CL addresses the challenge of adapting models to a dynamic data distribution arriving in a sequence, mitigating forgetting previously acquired knowledge. CL provides context for how models should learn and adapt to a continuous data stream over time.

This paper focuses on the DIL scenario [8], where a model learns to adapt to a sequence of domains over time. Each domain represents a variation of the same task, such as recognizing objects in different lighting conditions or weather scenarios. DIL is particularly relevant in applications where the same set of classes needs to be recognized across varying domains or conditions, making it crucial for real-world adaptive systems.

3 Merging LoRAs

We propose an adaptive LoRA merging approach for DIL tasks. Specifically, we want to address a limitation of current merging algorithms, *i.e.* the fact that they require fixed weights that are often difficult to select by hand and mostly assume that each task has equal importance, which significantly impacts the network performance.

Given a pre-trained model M and a sequence of domains $\mathcal{D} = \{D_1, D_2, \dots, D_N\}$, our goal is to learn a set of LoRA adapters $\mathcal{A} = \{A_1, A_2, \dots, A_N\}$ and merging coefficients $\alpha = \{\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_N\}$ that optimize performance across all seen domains. The core of our approach is the dynamical computation of the merging coefficients. For a set of n adapters, our method learns coefficients $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is computed as:

$$\alpha_i = \sigma(c_i) \cdot b \quad (2)$$

Algorithm 1 Adaptive LoRA Merging

- 1: **for** $D_k \in \{D_1, \dots, D_n\}$ **do**
- 2: Train a LoRA adapter A_k on D_k
- 3: Update the merging coefficients to include A_k
- 4: Construct balanced dataset D_{bal} from $\{D_1, \dots, D_k\}$
- 5: Learn new coefficients $\alpha = \{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_k\}$ by minimizing:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{coeff}} = \mathbb{E}_{(x,y) \sim \mathcal{D}_{\text{bal}}} [\mathcal{L}_{\text{CE}}(M(x; \underbrace{\sum_{i=1}^k \alpha_i A_i}_{\text{model + merged adapters}}, y)]$$

- 6: Merge adapters: $A_{\text{merged}} = \sum_{i=1}^k \alpha_i A_i$
 - 7: Evaluate A_{merged} on all seen domains D_1, \dots, D_k
 - 8: **end for**
-

Figure 1: Workflow of the approach

where $\sigma(\cdot)$ denotes the sigmoid function and c_i are learnable parameters. The bias term b is constrained to be positive and bounded:

$$b = 1 + (b_{\text{max}} - 1) \cdot \sigma(b_{\text{raw}}) \quad (3)$$

where b_{raw} is a learnable parameter and b_{max} is a hyperparameter defining the maximum possible bias. This formulation ensures that $0 < \alpha_i < b_{\text{max}}$, allowing for adaptive scaling while preventing excessive growth of coefficient values. Such weights are learned via standard backpropagation, using a balanced subset across all seen domains.

Our incremental learning process is described formally in Algorithm 1, while a graphical overview of the workflow can be seen in Figure 1. This process allows for continuous adaptation to new domains while dynamically adjusting the influence of previous ones. Unlike batch learning approaches, our method doesn't require retraining on data from all domains and maintains a compact model size by merging adapters.

In summary, our adaptive merging can be seen as a generalization of existing methods:

$$A_{\text{adaptive}} = \sum_{i=1}^k \alpha_i(\theta) A_i \quad (4)$$

where $\alpha_i(\theta)$ are learned, domain-specific coefficients parameterized by θ . In contrast, linear merging uses fixed weights, while TIES and DARE-TIES use binary or random masks with pruning operators. This adaptive nature allows our method to better capture the relationships between domains and adjust the merging strategy as new domains are encountered, leading to improved performance in domain incremental learning scenarios.

4 Results

In our experiments, we employed the Vision Transformer [1] as the base model, obtained through the `timm` library [10]. For the *state-of-the-art* merging algorithms, we selected three methods,

Table 1: Average accuracies (% , \uparrow) on PACS and OfficeHome. \mathbf{W} indicates the value of the fixed coefficient for each adapter, while b_{\max} is the maximum possible bias. We used 1 sample per class (*SPC*) to learn the adaptive coefficients. The results are obtained by averaging the accuracies across 3 different runs.

<i>SPC</i> = 1		<i>Fixed Coefficients</i>			<i>Adaptive Coefficients</i>		
Merging Algorithm		$\mathbf{W} = 1$	$\mathbf{W} = 3$	$\mathbf{W} = 5$	$b_{\max} = 1.0$	$b_{\max} = 3.0$	$b_{\max} = 5.0$
PACS	Task Arithmetic	29.19 \pm 9.99	11.38 \pm 4.76	13.34 \pm 6.57	76.48 \pm 14.65	29.72 \pm 10.15	17.84 \pm 4.44
	TIES	82.42 \pm 11.76	25.19 \pm 9.86	16.14 \pm 4.90	62.62 \pm 10.10	82.62 \pm 11.39	80.44 \pm 12.38
	DARE TIES	20.37 \pm 5.02	42.58 \pm 8.88	63.25 \pm 14.10	16.42 \pm 4.93	20.41 \pm 5.27	25.02 \pm 5.69
OfficeHome	Task Arithmetic	1.83 \pm 0.63	1.50 \pm 0.29	1.77 \pm 0.34	42.09 \pm 5.95	2.17 \pm 0.58	1.58 \pm 0.53
	TIES	66.83 \pm 6.92	2.17 \pm 0.42	2.16 \pm 0.65	24.88 \pm 3.51	62.95 \pm 5.17	62.74 \pm 5.83
	DARE TIES	2.65 \pm 0.30	13.50 \pm 2.32	34.12 \pm 4.85	1.68 \pm 0.20	2.72 \pm 0.21	3.18 \pm 0.21

namely Linear, TIES and DARE+TIES, using the implementation available in the `peft` library from HuggingFace [7]. For simplicity, we limited the hyperparameter search for the merging weights by imposing the same integer value to all adapters. We assessed existing merging algorithms and our approach against two benchmarks, designed explicitly for DIL. We used PACS [6] and OfficeHome [9], two real-world datasets with four distinct domains related to the same classification task.

Table 1 shows the results on the two benchmarks. We report the performance of the three algorithms with different values of fixed weights on the left and their behavior with learned coefficients on the right. Firstly, by examining the experiments with fixed coefficients, we can see that in both cases TIES obtains the best result overall, with the value for the weights equal to 1. Nonetheless, such algorithms require extensive manual selection of the hyperparameters. The table demonstrates that different coefficient values significantly impact accuracy, and if picked wrongly, this can lead to poor results when working in a DIL scenario.

We overcome this limitation with our *Adaptive LoRA Merging* approach. Similar to the fixed coefficients case, we experimented with different values of b_{\max} . The right-hand side of Table 1 shows that TIES achieves the best accuracy, improving the fixed coefficient algorithm in the case of PACS. For efficiency reasons, we used just 1 sample per class for our experiments, yet we obtained comparable results to the fixed coefficients case.

To thoroughly analyze our approach, we tested it using 5 samples per class as a memory buffer. The results are reported in Table 2. These results show a slight improvement when using a larger memory buffer, though it comes at a higher computational cost. Nonetheless, these findings suggest that our method does not require large buffers and can perform nearly optimally even with minimal memory.

Table 2: Average accuracies (% , \uparrow) for the PACS dataset. We used 5 samples per class (*SPC*) to learn the adaptive coefficients. The results are obtained by averaging the accuracies across 3 different runs.

<i>SPC</i> = 5		PACS			OfficeHome		
Merging Algorithm		$b_{\max} = 1.0$	$b_{\max} = 3.0$	$b_{\max} = 5.0$	$b_{\max} = 1.0$	$b_{\max} = 3.0$	$b_{\max} = 5.0$
Task Arithmetic		77.88 \pm 14.08	30.64 \pm 9.86	18.01 \pm 4.14	58.91 \pm 4.87	42.61 \pm 5.13	13.25 \pm 2.33
TIES		61.61 \pm 8.35	82.84 \pm 10.53	81.63 \pm 11.54	18.29 \pm 2.29	25.26 \pm 2.83	40.29 \pm 3.74
DARE TIES		16.35 \pm 4.92	20.18 \pm 5.20	24.51 \pm 5.52	1.61 \pm 0.22	1.69 \pm 0.20	1.83 \pm 0.21

Standard merging methods have a large hyperparameter space, significantly increasing the computational cost of manually selecting them. Our approach removes the need to select by hand the values of the weights by introducing b_{\max} as a single new value. Looking at the results, we argue that b_{\max} makes the model more robust to the hyperparameter selection compared to \mathbf{W} , leading to smaller performance variations and higher accuracy in the worst-case scenario. Additionally, our method reduces the complexity of hyperparameter selection by replacing adapter-specific weights with a single b_{\max} , significantly decreasing the number of hyperparameters.

5 Conclusion and Future Work

In this study, we explored applying PEFT techniques to DIL tasks. In particular, this work represents the first attempt at applying LoRA adapters and merging algorithms to CL scenarios.

We first analyzed the behavior of existing *state-of-the-art* merging methods when applied to dynamic contexts, finding that TIES achieves the highest accuracy over the other two algorithms. Nonetheless, we observed that such approaches require fixed coefficients, which are challenging to select manually

and do not adapt well to evolving environments.

To address this problem, we proposed a *end-to-end* learning algorithm, which learns to select the values of the coefficients based on the relevance of each adapter. We showed that our method performs similarly or even better to the fixed merging approach without needing complex and tedious hyperparameter selection.

This study marks a preliminary step in applying LoRA adapters to CL tasks. In future work, we intend to extend our method to other CL scenarios, such as Class-Incremental Learning, and more complex benchmarks featuring more classes and domains.

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